

РАЗРАБОТКА БЕЗОТХОДНОГО ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ЦИКЛА В НЕФТЕПЕРЕРАБОТКЕ

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7483034>

At present, oil refineries Republic, in the process of extraction purification of diesel fuel waste accumulates in the form of "acid tars". In appearance it is viscous mass of dark color with a density of 1.09 g/sm³ with a characteristic odor. AT in its composition, it contains over 50% organic substances, including:

- sulfonic acids32-35%
- oils..... 14 - 18%
- mineral part 4-5%
- water 28 -32%
- mechanical impurities4-6%
- sulfuric acid..... 5-7%
- sulfur4-5%

The hydrogen ion index (pH) is below 7, that is, it is an acidic environment. The amount and composition of the generated waste depends on the volume production and ongoing technological process. From a modern point of view of environmental protection and creation non-waste production implementation of waste disposal oil refining

– acid tar involves the following conditions:

- neutralization of acid tars to standard values neutralization,536
- preparation for processing of acid tars of extraction cleaning diesel fuel;
- development of a composition for obtaining a fixing composition when metal casting for metallurgical production.
- development of a composition for the preparation of anti-corrosion waterproofing material.

We offer acid sludge neutralization technology (pH=7) composition consisting of local inorganic secondary raw materials chemical production and dewatering agent. If acid tar is not neutralized, then in contact with metal corrosion occurs, which is highly undesirable process. because in the future, during their processing, various physicochemical processes take place with the formation of new substances that hinder them application. Based on neutralized acid huron

with the addition of vat residue from the distillation process of carboxylic acids and organic thinner, a composition will be obtained for fixing sand molds when metal casting (cast iron products). This product is in demand domestic market (Bekabad Iron and Steel Works, Almalksky Mining and Metallurgical Plant, Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Plant), and on the foreign market - metallurgical enterprises Russia and Kazakhstan.

Based on acid huron with the addition of the VAT residue of the process distillation of carboxylic acids, astringent, as well as organic diluent, a composition for the preparation will be obtained anticorrosive waterproofing material. anti-corrosion waterproofing material based on local raw materials is substitute for imported materials and is urgently needed especially in the northern regions of the republic (Karakalpakia, Khorezm, Bukhara) during waterproofing concrete foundations of buildings under construction and hydraulic structures (channels, reservoirs), as well as in the metro construction. All components used in new compositions are mainly secondary raw materials and production waste. Offered eco-technologies waste disposal is ensured by creating closed technological cycles in production and there is an improvement ecological situation in the republic.

Expected results and their meaning:

As a result of the project, the following results will be obtained:

- foreign experience in recycling will be studied and analyzed solid and liquid wastes of oil refining;
 - on the basis of acid tar, the composition and formulation will be developed:
 - a) compositions for hardening sand molds during metal casting (KUPF)
 - b) anticorrosive waterproofing material (GIM)
 - c) laboratory prototypes of GIM and CUPF537 were received
 - d) their physical and chemical properties have been studied and tested
 - e) standards will be developed for new product samples enterprises (STP)
 - f) new types of products will be additionally received
- In general, this will create a waste-free technological cycle in oil refining, reduce the cost of production, provide materials and energy saving in the industry, will create new jobs;
- due to the utilization of acid tar, an improvement will be provided environmental situation at work and in the country as a whole.

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